

ON A NOVEL TEST FOR DETERMINING THE MATRIX-THREAD BOND STRENGTH IN STITCHED CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Many tests to determine the strength of the fibre/matrix interface consist of testing a fibre encased in a resin coupon. The results of such a test are debateable as many factors are not accounted for. Thus a novel test to determine the interfacial shear strength of a Kevlar thread in a composite laminate has been developed. A difference of nearly 250% in the calculated interfacial shear stress has been found depending on whether a resin or composite coupon is used. A study of the surface of the commercially available Kevlar thread revealed significant contamination. Some of the thread was subsequently cleaned and plasma-treated. Using the novel pull-out test, it was found that the treated Kevlar thread had a notable improvement in the thread/matrix adhesion. However, the surface treatment was found to damage the tensile strength of the thread.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composite laminates have a considerable potential for utilization in weight critical applications. However, their commercial usage has been severely undermined by low interlaminar fracture toughness. Extensive research efforts have been devoted to the development of fibre-reinforced composites of higher mechanical capability, structural reliability and delamination resistance. Most have focussed on the use of tougher resins or better fibre-matrix interfaces [1]. Unfortunately, research in the area has resulted in only small improvements in the overall properties of the composite. However, modification of the fibre architecture, using existing textile technologies to introduce through-thickness fibres, has been observed to significantly improve the delamination resistance of a composite structure [1-4]. Of all the methods that are readily available, stitching is probably the simplest and most versatile.

The addition of through-thickness reinforcement by stitching has been reported to give large improvements in both the mode I and mode II delamination toughness but reductions in the in-plane properties [2,3,4]. The loss of in-plane properties has been attributed to failure at the stitch-line when samples are subjected to in-plane loading [4]. Fracture, debonding and pull-out of the thread is considered to be a major contributing energy absorbing mechanism in the failure of specimens tested in mode I and mode II [4]. Thus, knowledge of the bond strength between the stitching thread and the matrix is essential not only to the understanding of the failure mechanisms of stitched composites under in-plane and out-of-plane loading situations but also to the ability to model the behaviour of stitched composites.

The experimental methods for characterizing the fibre-matrix interface during recent years have relied on the use of single fibre-matrix adhesion tests [5-7]. Most of these methods rely on either pulling a fibre out of a block, disk or droplet of resin or fragmenting a fibre which has been encapsulated in a resin coupon. However pulling a thread out of resin is an unrealistic test as the effect of high fibre-volume fraction, the interfibre spacing, moisture and solvent sorption, thermal effects and deformation of the thread during fabrication are not accounted for [5,8]. Thus a test where the thread is pulled out of a composite laminate has been devised.

The authors have studied the effect of pulling a thread from both a resin block and a composite laminate. The effect of thread surface treatment on the interfacial shear strength and the thread tensile strength has also been determined.

MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURE

Unidirectional laminates of varying thickness were manufactured from a high strength, PAN-based carbon fibre (Tenax HTA) and an epoxy using a commercially available prepreg (Ciba-Geigy HTA/913). The prepreg packs were vacuumed extensively during the lay-up to ensure good quality laminates. The uncured laminates were stitched by hand after the lay-up procedure was complete. Initially laminates were cured in an autoclave with a vacuum bag procedure using the manufacturers recommended time/temperature/pressure profile. However, the pull-out samples manufactured using this technique displayed extensive thread damage at the surface of the laminate which rendered them unusable. Thus a fabrication procedure where the stitched laminates were cured without pressure or vacuum was implemented. It was expected that significant increases in resin volume fraction and laminate thickness would eventuate but the use of extensive vacuum during the layup minimized this (Table 1).

TABLE 1: Comparison of fibre volume fractions (determined by matrix digestion and burn-off techniques) and laminate thickness of a 22-ply Ciba-Geigy HTA/913 panel.

		AUTOCLAVED	NON-AUTOCLAVED
thickness (mm)		2.97 mm	3.02 mm
unstitched V_f	burnoff	64.6%	65.5%
	matrix	66.2%	64.7%
stitched V_f	burnoff	65.1%	64.1%
	matrix	65.8%	64.9%

Resin blocks were manufactured from Ciba-Geigy 913 epoxy and cured using the same time/temperature profile as the laminate samples.

The thread used was a commercially available twisted two-ply Kevlar 29 yarn. The diameter was 0.12mm. The most common use for such a thread is in the manufacture of fireproof clothing. Thus little care is taken during the manufacture, storage and transportation to ensure the thread remains clean. A preliminary investigation using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) revealed significant surface contamination. An amount of the thread was cleaned by solvent extraction in a cold Soxhlet extractor followed by drying under vacuum. An ammonia plasma treatment was then carried out [9,10]. Pull-out samples have been manufactured using the thread in both the as-available and cleaned conditions.

TEST METHODS

PULL-OUT TESTS

The pull-out test is simple to perform (figure 1). Control of the fibre embedded length is critical, to obtain a range of embedded lengths [6]. The embedded length was varied by selecting a different number of prepreg plies during fabrication. The pulling out of a fibre has the potential for differences in technique, the most obvious of which is the loading rate. Alignment of the fibre with the loading axis is also a major source of error. Despite these problems the number of sources of error is small [5-8].

Figure 1: Schematic representation of a thread pull-out sample.

A steadily increasing force was applied to the free end of the fibre using a servo-hydraulic Instron materials testing machine at a cross-head speed of 1mm/min. The force and displacement were recorded. From a typical plot (figure 2) a number of characteristic loads, P_o , the initial debonding load, P^* , the maximum debonding load and P_f , the frictional pull-out load, can be determined. and thus the related stresses σ_o , σ^* and σ_f calculated. The debond shear strength, τ_b , was determined using the Hsueh model [11] which takes the form

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma^*}{dL}\right)_{L=0} = \frac{2\tau_b[1 + (\gamma/\alpha)]}{d}$$

where d is the diameter of the thread and L the embedded length of the thread which was taken as being the thickness of the composite. The initial gradient of the maximum debond stress versus the embedded length curve (figure 4) was used and γ/α approaches zero due to the sample dimensions.

Figure 2: Typical load vs displacement plot for thread pull-out.

THREAD TENSILE TESTS

The tensile strength and Young's moduli of the untreated and treated threads were measured following the ASTM standard tensile test method for textile threads (D2256 and D3217). Tests for both the standard tensile sample and a sample which imitates a stitch (loop strength) were carried out. A servo-hydraulic Instron materials testing machine with a data acquisition system was used to apply the load to samples of varying gauges lengths at several different cross-head speeds. The data reduction was accomplished using both Weibull and Gaussian distributions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The failure modes of stitched samples during bulk property tests indicates the importance of the thread properties (figure 3). Whilst a loss in tensile strength of about 5% results with stitching, large improvements of over ten-fold and two-fold in the mode I and II delamination fracture toughness respectively have been found. It is thought the fracture, debonding and pull-out of the thread is the major energy absorbing mechanism which contributes to these significant improvements.

To characterize the debonding and pull-out (interfacial) shear stress, lengths of the Kevlar thread were pulled out of both resin blocks and composite laminates. The maximum debond stress, σ^* (which is derived from P^*), was plotted against the embedded length (figure 4). The stresses rose to a maximum and then plateaued with increasing length. The debond shear stress, τ_b , and the asymptotic debond stress, $\bar{\sigma}$, which is related to the differential shrinkage during cooling from the fabrication temperature [11], can be easily determined (Table 2).

TABLE 2: Interfacial shear stresses determined for pull-out of a untreated and treated two-ply Kevlar 29 thread from composite laminates and resin blocks.

SAMPLE	Debond shear stress, τ_b (MPa)	Asymptotic debond stress, $\bar{\sigma}$ (MPa)
Untreated thread from composite	23.8 MPa	1380 MPa
Treated thread from composite	29.2 MPa	1550 MPa
Untreated thread from resin stub	59.0 MPa	>3600 MPa

Figure 3: Fracture surface of a stitched CFRP tested in mode I showing a debonded and pulled out Kevlar thread.

Figure 4: The maximum debond strength, σ_o , vs embedded length plots for pull-out tests on (a) an untreated thread and (b) treated thread pulled out of a composite laminate and (c) an untreated thread pulled out of a resin stub.

Figure 5: Deformation of the thread and composite caused by the stitching process.

The interfacial shear stress was calculated as being nearly 250% higher when a resin rather than composite base was used (Table 2). The difference in results can be accounted for by considering the effects of high fibre volume fraction, interfibre spacing, different moisture and solvent sorption rates, thermal effects, deformation of the thread during fabrication and cure of uni-directional laminates (figure 5) and the limited amount of resin available in a prepreg laminate to bond the thread. The effect of these fabrication factors can be observed when the asymptotic debond stresses are compared. The $\bar{\sigma}$, which is a measure of the differential shrinkage effects, determined from the resin stub pull-out samples at least 250% higher than the $\bar{\sigma}$ determined for the composite pull-out samples.

The results of an XPS study have shown a significant amount of impurities on the surface of the Kevlar thread in the as-received condition. After a cleaning and plasma treatment the thread showed a considerably different surface chemistry with the nitrogen content near stoichiometric levels and a large decrease in trace impurities (Table 3). This indicates a larger London (dispersive) component of free surface energy which should result in a better matrix/fibre adhesion. Pull-out results show an improvement in the interfacial shear stress of about 25% after the surface treatment (Table 2).

TABLE 3: Results of XPS study of an as-received two-ply Kevlar thread and the same thread after a cleaning and plasma treatment.

SAMPLE	C (%)	O (%)	N (%)	Na (%)	Si (%)	F (%)	S (%)	Ca (%)
untreated	81.9*	10.3	1.6	1.1	2.8	1.0	0.5	0.8
treated	70.7	17.3	6.9	1.4	1.3			0.3

* carbon is 100% aliphatic rather than aromatic

Unfortunately, a decrease of 20% in the thread fracture strength was observed after the cleaning and plasma procedure. This decrease is even more apparent after stitching (25%). It is believed that some of the carbon-based and trace elements found on the surface of the thread by XPS may be deliberately added by the manufacturer to minimize friction between the thread and the stitching machine. An XPS study of cotton thread supports this theory. In addition it was noticed that the plasma thread was difficult to stitch with as it frequently jammed in the machine. It was found that data reduction using either a Gaussian or Weibull distribution yielded similar results.

TABLE 4: Tensile strengths of two-ply Kevlar 29 thread before and after stitching in both the standard and loop configurations.

		UNTREATED THREAD (MPa)	PLASMA-TREATED THREAD (MPa)
As-received		4790 MPa	3878 MPa
After stitching	needle	3709 MPa	2836 MPa
	bobbin	4172 MPa	3192 MPa
Loop As-received		3675 MPa	3185 MPa
After stitching	needle	3166 MPa	2589 MPa
	bobbin	3292 MPa	2643 MPa

CONCLUSION

A study of different thread pull-out test methods have shown a notable difference in results. The calculated interfacial shear stress varied by nearly 250% depending on whether the thread was pulled from a composite laminate or a resin block. An X-ray photoelectron spectra (XPS) obtained from the Kevlar thread indicated a significant amount of carbon-based and trace element contamination. A comparison of the interfacial shear strength of the as-received Kevlar thread with the same thread after surface treatment showed a 25% improvement. However, it was established that the surface treatment resulted in a 20% loss in thread tensile strength. This property loss was even worse after the thread after the thread had been stitched. The reason for this may be the removal of an anti-friction coating applied by the thread manufacturer.

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